

PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS' PERCEIVED EXTENT OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THEIR SCHOOL HEADS' INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 2

Pages: 210-227

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2952

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14729366

Manuscript Accepted: 12-31-2024

Public School Teachers' Perceived Extent of Implementation of their School Heads' Instructional Supervision

Vincent R. Cailing,* Diana A. Amper, Hairah O. Ali, Marie Gold C. Alonsabe,
Carlos T. Basadre, Olga C. Alonsabe

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Instructional supervision plays a crucial role in improving the quality of education and fostering teacher development. This study examined public school teachers' perceptions of the extent to which school heads implement instructional supervision and whether these perceptions vary across teachers' length of experience, educational attainment, and teaching position. This research utilized a descriptive-correlational design, with 121 public school teachers from Claveria, Misamis Oriental, as the sample. Stratified random sampling was used to select participants. A questionnaire, adopted from Comighud et al. (2020), was used to gather data. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: demographic information and perceptions of instructional supervision. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to present the demographic profile, while mean and standard deviation were used to assess teachers' views on five key aspects of instructional supervision: Concept and Purpose, Planning and Preparations, Organization and Implementation, Dialogue and Discussion, and Satisfaction and Evaluation. ANOVA was used to explore whether demographic factors influenced perceptions. The study's findings revealed that most respondents were in the middle stages of their careers, with many holding entry-level positions. Over half had pursued graduate studies, but none had completed a doctoral degree. Instructional supervision was generally perceived as being implemented to a very high extent, with the highest ratings in Concept and Purpose (mean = 4.48) and Dialogue and Discussion (mean = 4.41). However, the Planning and Preparations aspect received a lower score (mean = 4.12), indicating room for improvement. Experienced teachers showed different expectations in Concepts and Purpose, while no significant differences were found in perceptions of Organization and Implementation. Based on the findings, it is recommended that schools offer personalized professional development opportunities for teachers at different career stages, improve planning and preparation processes, and ensure that supervisory practices are flexible and supportive of teachers with varying levels of experience and education.

Keywords: *instructional supervision, school heads, teacher perceptions, educational attainment, teaching experience*

Introduction

Instructional supervision plays a vital role in improving the quality of education provided by teachers, ultimately leading to better student outcomes. This process goes beyond simply identifying mistakes; it is an opportunity for growth where school heads guide teachers to enhance their instructional strategies. According to Honculada (2022), recognizing teachers' needs during supervision fosters their improvement. Effective instructional supervision emphasizes professional development, enabling teachers to deliver more impactful lessons and improve student performance in assessments.

Educational reforms over the years have underscored the need to revisit and refine instructional supervision practices to align with innovations in education (Osman & Kamis, 2019). Historically, supervision has evolved from rigid bureaucratic practices to more democratic and participatory approaches (Tulowitzki, 2019). In this context, instructional supervision has emerged as a critical function of school leadership, influencing not only teachers' effectiveness but also the overall teaching-learning process (Agus & Samuri, 2018).

Research highlights the positive impact of instructional supervision on school performance. Irawan et al. (2018) found that schools with effective supervision often exhibit improved teaching practices and learning outcomes. Furthermore, Gordon (2019) emphasized that supervision helps teachers enhance their knowledge, skills, and decision-making capabilities. Oriente and Alvarado (2020) similarly noted that effective supervision addresses challenges such as poor student performance, advocating for improved supervision processes.

The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines highlights the importance of instructional supervision through key policies aimed at improving teaching and learning. DepEd Order No. 2, series of 2015, introduced the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), which encourages school leaders to focus on guiding and monitoring teachers to enhance their performance (Pomentel, 2024). Additionally, Republic Act No. 9155 emphasizes the dual role of school heads as both leaders in teaching and managers of school operations, ensuring they play an active role in supporting teachers' professional development. Hasim et al. (2022) highlighted that school heads are effective leaders, particularly in addressing challenges faced by teachers and students. They excel in supervising school operations and bringing out the best in the school, demonstrating competence not only in cognitive and psychomotor skills but also in emotional and interpersonal aspects. Furthermore, DepEd Order No. 42, series of 2017, reinforces that effective instructional supervision not only fosters teachers' growth but also improves students' academic performance (Limon, 2015). These policies underline the critical role of school leadership in building a supportive and productive teaching environment.

Effective instructional supervision involves strategies such as classroom observations, constructive feedback, and professional development facilitation (Marzano, 2019). These practices help foster a culture of continuous improvement, trust, and mutual respect between school heads and teachers (Pomentel, 2024). Teachers who perceive their supervisors as supportive and transparent are more likely to adopt positive attitudes toward instructional improvement (Zarco, 2024). However, the anxiety that some teachers feel during supervision must also be addressed through consistent and transparent feedback processes (Zarco, 2024).

This study examines how public-school teachers perceive the extent of their school heads' implementation of instructional supervision. Mendoza and Hife (2020) mentioned that it is crucial to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of instructional supervision practices. Data on supervision activities, teacher perceptions, student outcomes, and school improvement should be collected to inform improvement efforts. Drawing insights from previous research and current policies, it aims to shed light on the effectiveness of supervision practices in fostering teacher development and improving educational outcomes. By understanding these perceptions, school heads can better refine their supervisory approaches, ensuring alignment with educational goals and teacher needs.

Research Questions

The study addresses the following key problem statements:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Length of Teaching Experience;
 - 1.2. Educational Attainment; and
 - 1.3. Teaching Position?
2. What is the extent of implementation of the school heads' Instructional Supervision as perceived by public school teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. Concept and Purpose;
 - 2.2. Planning and Preparations;
 - 2.3. Organization and Implementation;
 - 2.4. Dialogue and Discussion; and
 - 2.5. Satisfaction and Evaluation?
3. Are there significant differences in the perceived extent of Implementation of their School Heads' Instructional Supervision among the respondents in terms of their:
 - 3.1. Length of Teaching Experience;
 - 3.2. Educational Attainment; and
 - 3.3. Teaching Position?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to give a detailed analysis of how much instructional supervision is implemented, based on the views of public-school teachers. Descriptive research is ideal for examining how teachers perceive the supervision practices in their schools.

Additionally, the study used a correlational research design to explore the relationships between different factors. Specifically, it looked at how the length of teaching experience, educational attainment, and teaching position affect teachers' views of their school heads' instructional supervision. The goal is to find patterns or connections that explain the differences in teachers' perceptions.

Respondents

This research included 121 public school teachers, elementary and secondary, as the sample. These teachers are currently teaching in one of the districts in Claveria, Division of Misamis Oriental. The sample size in this study was determined from the total population using Cochran's formula with a 5% error rate. Then, proportional stratified Random Sampling was used to determine the number of respondents from each level (See Table 1).

Table 1. *The Data Calculation of Proportionate Stratified Sampling*

<i>Level</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>
Elementary Teachers	118	82
Secondary Teachers	57	39
Total	175	121

Instrument

This research utilized a questionnaire adopted from Comighud, Futralan, and Cordevilla (2020) organized into two parts. Part one contained the profile of the teachers. Part two sought the data on the extent of implementation of instructional supervision.

The adopted survey questionnaire uses a 5-point Likert scale, where respondents choose from the following options: 1 - Strongly Disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Moderately Agree, 4 - Agree, and 5 - Strongly Agree. These responses were translated into the following interpretations of the extent of instructional supervision implementation:

Table 2. *Scoring Procedure for the Extent of Instructional Supervision Implementation*

Score	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent (VHE)
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent (HE)
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate Extent (ME)
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low Extent (LE)
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Extent (VLE)

Procedure

The researchers submitted a formal request letter to the Public Schools District In-Charge seeking approval to conduct the study. Once permission was granted, they collected essential data, including the population details of elementary and secondary school teachers in the district. Simultaneously, the researchers reached out to the original authors of the survey instrument via email to obtain permission to adopt their questionnaire. Approval was graciously granted by one of the authors, ensuring the tool's appropriate and ethical use.

To ensure convenience and accessibility, the survey was distributed electronically through Google Forms. Participation was entirely voluntary, with teachers explicitly assured of their anonymity and the confidentiality of their responses. Clear instructions were provided to foster understanding and encourage candid feedback, reflecting the study's commitment to ethical research practices.

Data Analysis

The data analysis used descriptive statistical methods to describe the respondents' demographic profiles, such as their length of teaching experience, educational attainment, and teaching positions. Frequencies and percentages were calculated to provide an overview of these characteristics. To understand how teachers view their school heads' instructional supervision, mean and standard deviation were computed for different aspects, including the concept and purpose; planning and preparations; organization and implementation; dialogue and discussion; and satisfaction and evaluation. Using ANOVA, the study also explored whether teachers' views on their school heads' instructional supervision differ based on their demographics. All data analysis was carried out using PSPP-GNU Statistical software.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to strict ethical standards to protect participants and maintain research integrity. Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, their rights to participate voluntarily, and their ability to withdraw at any time without consequences. Explicit consent was obtained before they completed the survey. Anonymity was ensured by distributing the survey electronically, with no identifiable information linked to the responses, and all data were securely stored to maintain confidentiality. Permission to conduct the study was sought and granted by the Public Schools District In-Charge, and the original authors of the survey instrument approved its use in this research. Participation was entirely voluntary, with assurances that involvement or non-involvement would not affect the teachers' professional standing or relationships. Additionally, the researchers ensured the accuracy and integrity of data collection, analysis, and reporting to avoid misleading results or interpretations.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of: Length of Teaching Experience, Educational Attainment, and Teaching Position?

Table 3 shows the teaching experience of 121 respondents, revealing a wide range of professional backgrounds.

Table 3. *Distribution of the Respondents' Length of Teaching Experience*

Length of Teaching Experience	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1-5 years	22	18.18
6-10 years	43	35.54
11-15 years	25	20.66
16-20 years	6	4.96
21-25 years	7	5.79
26 years and more	18	14.88
Total	121	100

The largest group, 43 respondents (35.54%), have 6-10 years of teaching experience, indicating many participants are in the middle stage of their careers. These teachers likely have enough experience to be confident in their roles but are still early in their professional

journey.

The second largest group includes 22 respondents (18.18%) with 1-5 years of experience, highlighting a considerable number of newer teachers just beginning their careers. Meanwhile, 25 respondents (20.66%) fall into the 11-15 years category, representing a group with significant experience and expertise.

The remaining participants are spread across longer teaching careers: 16-20 years (4.96%), 21-25 years (5.79%), and 26 years or more (14.88%). The smallest group is in the 16-20 years range, while those with over 26 years represent a noteworthy portion of veteran educators.

This mix of teaching experience provides a balanced representation of teachers at various career stages, with the largest portion being moderately experienced. Research underscores the importance of teaching experience. Kini and Podolsky (2016) explained that teachers improve significantly in their early years, with growth continuing even into their second and third decades. Rees (2015) emphasized that new teachers often seek additional training to better meet their professional needs. Aldeeb (2018) noted that experienced teachers are better at linking theory to practice, benefiting learners in meaningful ways. Similarly, Laabidi (2021) observed that experienced teachers are more likely to apply critical thinking strategies in their teaching, which enhances learning outcomes.

Table 4 presents the distribution of respondents' educational attainment, based on a sample of 121 participants.

Table 4. *Distribution of the Respondents' Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Bachelor's Degree	30	24.79
With Master's Units	62	51.24
With Master's Degree	11	9.09
With Doctoral Units	18	14.88
With Doctoral Degree	0	0.00
Total	121	100

The majority of respondents, 51.24% (62 individuals), have completed master's units, indicating that more than half of the sample has pursued graduate-level education but has not yet completed a master's degree. A significant portion, 24.79% (30 respondents), hold a bachelor's degree, reflecting that nearly a quarter of the participants have only completed their undergraduate studies.

In contrast, 9.09% (11 respondents) of the participants have obtained a master's degree, while a smaller group, 14.88% (18 individuals), have completed doctoral units, indicating they are pursuing or have pursued doctoral-level education but have not yet completed their doctoral degree. Notably, none of the respondents hold a doctoral degree, as indicated by the 0.00% in that category.

This data suggests that while a significant portion of the sample has pursued or is in the process of pursuing advanced education, very few have completed higher degrees such as a master's or doctoral degree. Pescuela (2015) noted that while many teachers pursue further studies to enhance their skills, only a few are expected to complete their degrees. In public schools, teachers are encouraged to fully complete their postgraduate studies, as professional career advancement is a key requirement for promotion to higher positions, a higher salary, and increased job responsibilities. Additionally, it helps in enhancing teachers' theoretical and technical knowledge. The predominance of respondents with master's units and the lack of respondents with a doctoral degree may reflect a trend where teachers are advancing their education but have not yet completed higher qualifications.

Research consistently shows that teacher qualifications significantly impact student outcomes. Higher educational attainment of teachers is associated with improved student performance on licensure exams and greater likelihood of students earning higher-level degrees (Balanquit et al., 2023; Lee & Lee, 2020). Specifically, teachers with doctoral degrees positively influence student performance, while those with only bachelor's degrees have an inverse relationship (Balanquit et al., 2023). Teacher certification and experience are particularly important for children in disadvantaged schools, such as rural and public institutions (Nyatsikor et al., 2020). The benefits of education extend beyond academic achievement, as higher educational attainment is linked to increased individual earnings, improved standard of living, and upward social mobility (Hussein, 2021). These findings underscore the importance of investing in teacher education and professional development to enhance student outcomes and societal progress, with implications for education policies worldwide (Lee & Lee, 2020; Nyatsikor et al., 2020).

Table 5. presents the distribution of the respondents' teaching positions among a sample of 121 participants.

Table 5. *Distribution of the Respondents' Teaching Positions*

<i>Teaching Position</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Teacher I	74	61.16
Teacher II	8	6.61
Teacher III	31	25.62
Master Teacher I	4	3.31
Master Teacher II	4	3.31
Total	121	100

The data reveals that the majority of respondents hold the position of Teacher I, accounting for 61.16% (74 individuals). This indicates that a significant portion of the sample consists of teachers in the early stages of their careers, as Teacher I is typically an entry-level position.

A smaller proportion of the respondents, 25.62% (31 individuals), are in the position of Teacher III, suggesting that a considerable number of teachers have gained more experience and have advanced beyond the initial stages of their careers. Teacher II holds 6.61% (8 respondents) of the positions, indicating that this mid-level role is less common among the sample group.

The positions of Master Teacher I and Master Teacher II are represented by the smallest proportions, each accounting for 3.31% (4 respondents). These roles are typically associated with teachers who have considerable experience and expertise, often serving as mentors or leaders within the school. The low representation in these positions suggests that while there is some level of leadership within the group, the majority of respondents are in more junior teaching roles.

In summary, the data indicates that the sample is predominantly composed of early-career teachers, with a smaller number advancing to mid-level or leadership positions. This distribution reflects the overall career progression of teachers within the sample, with fewer individuals holding higher-level teaching or leadership positions.

Research highlights the value of experience in teaching. Aldeeb (2018) emphasized that experienced teachers are better at connecting theory to practice, enhancing student outcomes. Kini and Podolsky (2016) noted that teachers' effectiveness improves significantly in their early years and continues to grow throughout their careers. Additionally, Mufidah et al. (2021) found that training and experience play a key role in improving teacher performance.

Problem 2 What is the extent of implementation of the school heads' Instructional Supervision as perceived by public school teachers in terms of: Concept and Purpose, Planning and Preparations, Organization and Implementation, Dialogue and Discussion; and, Satisfaction and Evaluation?

Table 6 presents the results of the respondents' perceptions of instructional supervision in terms of its concept and purpose. The responses are categorized by specific items, with weighted mean (WM) and standard deviation (SD) values provided for each.

Table 6. Instructional Supervision in Terms of Concept and Purpose

<i>Items</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
a. Concept of Instructional Supervision			
Instructional Supervision is ...			
1. a model of a collaborative classroom instruction	4.51	.50	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. a tool to promote shared instructional decisions	4.55	.50	Very High Extent (VHE)
3. a means to define the roles of teachers in teaching instruction	4.55	.55	Very High Extent (VHE)
4. a mechanism to provide instructional directions	4.60	.54	Very High Extent (VHE)
5. an avenue for situational approach of instructional supervision	4.55	.50	Very High Extent (VHE)
Composite	4.55	.45	Very High Extent (VHE)
b. Purpose of Instructional Supervision			
Instructional Supervision ...			
1. promotes cooperative work among instructional leaders and classroom teachers	4.50	.61	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. improves instructional practices, student achievement and classroom management	4.45	.61	Very High Extent (VHE)
3. considers the specific needs and developmental stages of individual teachers	4.43	.69	Very High Extent (VHE)
4. focuses on teacher's knowledge, skills and ability towards curriculum improvement and staff development	4.39	.71	Very High Extent (VHE)
5. analyses and makes judgments about teacher's instructional efficiency and effectiveness	4.18	.90	High Extent (HE)
Composite	4.39	.57	Very High Extent (VHE)
Overall	4.48	.47	Very High Extent (VHE)

Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Strongly Agree (Very High Extent - VHE); 3.41–4.20 – Agree (High Extent - HE); 2.61–3.40 – Moderately Agree (Moderate Extent - ME); 1.81–2.60 – Disagree (Low Extent - LE); 1.00–1.80 – Strongly Disagree (Very Low Extent - VLE)

The concept of instructional supervision is generally perceived to be of very high extent (VHE) by the respondents. The five items related to the concept all received high mean scores, ranging from 4.51 to 4.60. The item with the highest score (4.60, SD = .54) is "Instructional supervision is a mechanism to provide instructional directions," suggesting that respondents strongly agree with the idea that instructional supervision plays a critical role in guiding teachers' instructional practices. This is consistent with Glickman et al. (2018), who emphasize that instructional supervision should provide clear direction and support for improving teaching practices. Additionally, the items "a tool to promote shared instructional decisions" and "a means to define the roles of teachers in teaching instruction" both scored 4.55, suggesting that respondents also view instructional supervision as a collaborative process that clearly outlines teachers' roles in improving instructional quality, as noted in the work of Sergiovanni and Starratt (2007), who highlight the importance of collaborative supervision in fostering teacher development.

The composite mean score for the concept of instructional supervision is 4.55 (SD = .45), indicating a very high extent of agreement that instructional supervision encompasses collaboration, clarity in roles, and guidance. This aligns with Glickman, Gordon, and Ross-

Gordon’s (2018) assertion that effective instructional supervision involves continuous reflection and growth within a supportive environment.

The purpose of instructional supervision is also rated as having a very high extent (VHE) overall, with a composite mean score of 4.39 (SD = .57). The items measuring the purpose of instructional supervision focus on its role in promoting collaboration, improving teaching practices, and addressing the needs of individual teachers. The highest-rated item in this section is “Instructional supervision is a tool to promote cooperative work among instructional leaders and classroom teachers,” with a mean score of 4.50 (SD = .61), reinforcing the idea that effective supervision promotes a collaborative environment between school leaders and teachers (Bauer et al., 2015).

Other items such as “improves instructional practices, student achievement, and classroom management” (WM = 4.45, SD = .61) and “considers the specific needs and developmental stages of individual teachers” (WM = 4.43, SD = .69) further support the notion that instructional supervision is viewed as a vehicle for improving both individual teacher performance and overall school outcomes, consistent with the views of Haramain et al. (2023) and Comighud et al. (2020), who argue that supervision should be developmental and personalized to the needs of the teacher.

The item “analyses and makes judgments about teacher’s instructional efficiency and effectiveness” received a slightly lower mean score of 4.18 (SD = .90), reflecting a high extent (HE) agreement, indicating that while this aspect of supervision is acknowledged, it might be viewed less favorably as it could be perceived as evaluative. This perception aligns with the concerns highlighted by Mamo and Nigussa (2019), who noted that some teachers might view certain supervisory activities as judgmental rather than supportive.

Overall, the data indicates that respondents perceive instructional supervision in terms of both concept and purpose to be highly beneficial in fostering collaboration, improving teaching practices, and supporting teacher development. The composite mean scores for both the concept (4.55) and purpose (4.39) of instructional supervision and the overall weighted mean of 4.48 are in the very high extent (VHE) range, suggesting that teachers and school leaders alike recognize the importance of effective supervisory practices in enhancing instructional quality and school improvement.

This perception is supported by the literature, including Glickman et al. (2018), who emphasize the importance of supportive, collaborative, and developmental supervisory practices, and Bauer et al. (2015), who highlight that effective instructional supervision should focus on fostering positive teacher performance through trust, communication, and shared decision-making. The relatively lower score for the item related to evaluating teacher effectiveness (4.18) suggests that while instructional supervision is broadly seen as positive, there may be a need to balance developmental support with evaluative functions to ensure continued teacher engagement and professional growth.

The data in Table 7 reveals the perceptions of teachers regarding the effectiveness of instructional supervision, specifically focusing on Advance Notifications and Planning Lessons with Supervisors and Informal Visitations and Classroom Observations.

Table 7. *Instructional Supervision in Terms of Planning and Preparations*

<i>Items</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
a. Advance Notifications and Planning Lessons with Supervisors			
Instructional Supervisor...			
1. keeps teachers aware of the conduct of instructional supervision	4.66	.54	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. notifies teachers of classroom visitations and lesson observations	4.60	.55	Very High Extent (VHE)
3. sets up specific sessions with the teachers to discuss curriculum implementation	4.43	.74	Very High Extent (VHE)
4. provides teachers with adequate information to become familiar with supervision of instruction	4.56	.66	Very High Extent (VHE)
5. involves teachers in the planning and preparation of the delivery of classroom lessons	4.46	.73	Very High Extent (VHE)
Composite	4.54	.58	Very High Extent (VHE)
b. Informal Visitations and Classroom Observations			
Instructional Supervisor...			
1. informally visits teachers in their respective classes during teaching instruction	3.53	1.03	High Extent (HE)
2. monitors teachers outside the classroom during real-world lesson application	3.47	1.09	High Extent (HE)
3. supervise teachers on a regular basis inside the classroom during curriculum implementation	3.95	.89	High Extent (HE)
4. enters the classroom as unobtrusively as possible in the conduct of lesson observations	3.64	.98	High Extent (HE)
5. capitalize the expertise of teachers to share supervisory knowledge, skills and information	3.88	.84	High Extent (HE)
Composite	3.70	.75	High Extent (HE)
Overall	4.12	.57	High Extent (HE)

Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Strongly Agree (Very High Extent - VHE); 3.41–4.20 – Agree (High Extent - HE); 2.61–3.40 – Moderately Agree (Moderate Extent - ME); 1.81–2.60 – Disagree (Low Extent - LE); 1.00–1.80 – Strongly Disagree (Very Low Extent - VLE)

In terms of Advance Notifications and Planning Lessons with Supervisors, teachers reported a very high extent (VHE) of implementation, with a composite mean of 4.54, indicating that instructional supervisors are highly effective in preparing teachers for supervisory activities. Among the items in this category, the statement “keeps teachers aware of the conduct of instructional supervision” received the highest mean of 4.66, which signifies that teachers feel well-informed about upcoming supervisory activities. This finding aligns with Marzano (2019) and Pomentel (2024), who emphasize the importance of proactive communication between supervisors and teachers. Similarly, the item “notifies teachers of classroom visitations and lesson observations” also received a high mean of 4.60, further supporting the notion that advance notification is a valued practice. These items reflect a strong, well-organized approach to instructional supervision, ensuring that teachers feel prepared and supported.

In contrast, the aspect of Informal Visitations and Classroom Observations received a composite mean of 3.70, indicating a high extent (HE) but suggesting that there is room for improvement in these activities. Among the items in this aspect, the item “supervises teachers on a regular basis inside the classroom during curriculum implementation” received the highest mean of 3.95, signaling that regular classroom observations during teaching are perceived positively by teachers. This finding is consistent with Irawan et al. (2018), who emphasized the positive impact of regular classroom observations on school performance. Another item, “capitalizes on the expertise of teachers to share supervisory knowledge, skills, and information,” also received a high mean of 3.88, which suggests that teachers value the sharing of knowledge and expertise during informal observations. However, this aspect also highlights a need for more frequent and impactful visitations, as indicated by the lower composite mean compared to the planning and preparation aspect.

The overall 4.12 mean suggests that instructional supervision is perceived as effective to a high extent, with a strong emphasis on advance notifications and planning lessons with supervisors. These practices align well with best practices in instructional leadership, as described by Pomentel (2024) and Tschannen-Moran & Hoy (2016), who stress the importance of collaboration, trust, and feedback in supervisory relationships. However, improvements in the frequency and quality of informal visitations and classroom observations could further enhance the supervisory process, as highlighted by Zarco (2024), who noted the potential for reducing teacher anxiety through more supportive and transparent practices.

In summary, instructional supervisors can continue to build on their strengths in preparation and communication but should place greater emphasis on increasing the regularity and depth of informal classroom observations to foster teacher growth and improve teaching effectiveness.

Table 8. *Instructional Supervision in Terms of Organization and Implementation*

Items	WM	SD	Interpretation
a. Lesson Plan Review			
Instructional supervisor examines teacher’s ...			
1. formulation of behavioral learning objectives	4.23	.67	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. organization of K-to-12 learning content	4.07	.84	High Extent (HE)
3. utilization of innovative teaching strategies	4.17	.76	High Extent (HE)
4. consumption of updated teaching references	4.13	.88	High Extent (HE)
5. use of appropriate instructional devices	4.16	.84	High Extent (HE)
6. preparation of meaningful learning experiences	4.32	.89	Very High Extent (VHE)
7. communication of higher order thinking skills	4.26	.79	Very High Extent (VHE)
8. construction of objective-oriented assessment	4.17	.84	High Extent (HE)
9. application of learnt concept to real-life setting	4.22	.80	Very High Extent (VHE)
10. provision of skills-based enrichment	4.21	.82	Very High Extent (VHE)
Composite	4.19	.76	High Extent (HE)
b. Actual Classroom Observation			
Instructional supervisor examines teacher’s ...			
1. preparation of functional lesson plans or appropriate daily logs	4.31	.74	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. implementation of K-to-12 based curricular instruction or classroom lessons	4.25	.72	Very High Extent (VHE)
3. organization of classroom practices or teaching procedures	4.28	.73	Very High Extent (VHE)
4. establishment of classroom discipline and routine management	4.33	.79	Very High Extent (VHE)
5. accomplishment of school forms, teaching records, and learners’ reports	4.23	.80	Very High Extent (VHE)
Composite	4.28	.71	Very High Extent (VHE)
Overall	4.22	.73	Very High Extent (VHE)

Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Strongly Agree (Very High Extent - VHE); 3.41–4.20 – Agree (High Extent - HE); 2.61–3.40 – Moderately Agree (Moderate Extent - ME); 1.81–2.60 – Disagree (Low Extent - LE); 1.00–1.80 – Strongly Disagree (Very Low Extent - VLE)

Lesson Plan Review has a composite mean of 4.19, which falls under the category of High Extent (HE). The individual items in this section show a strong focus on ensuring quality lesson planning. The highest mean within this aspect is for the item “preparation of meaningful learning experiences”, with a mean of 4.32, interpreted as Very High Extent (VHE). This suggests that instructional supervisors place a significant emphasis on ensuring that lesson plans are designed to create meaningful learning opportunities for students. Additionally, the item “communication of higher-order thinking skills” received a high mean of 4.26, indicating a focus on fostering critical thinking in students. Items like “formulation of behavioral learning objectives” and “construction of objective-oriented assessment”, with means of 4.23 and 4.17, respectively, show that supervisors are attentive to the structure and clarity of learning objectives and assessments.

On the other hand, the Actual Classroom Observation aspect has a composite mean of 4.28, categorized as Very High Extent (VHE), indicating that teachers perceive a high level of support during actual classroom observations. The highest mean in this category is for “establishment of classroom discipline and routine management”, with a mean of 4.33, interpreted as VHE. This item underscores the importance of maintaining an organized and disciplined classroom, which is a crucial factor in the effectiveness of teaching. Other items like “preparation of functional lesson plans” (mean = 4.31) and “implementation of K-to-12 based curricular instruction” (mean = 4.25) also received high scores, suggesting that classroom observations are centered on evaluating the preparedness and execution of the lesson.

The findings indicate that the practice of instructional supervision is highly effective in ensuring that teachers prepare meaningful learning experiences and maintain discipline in the classroom. These results align with the work of Ogbo (2015), who posited that supervision is a tool for maximizing a teacher’s professional development. Similarly, the importance of effective supervision in ensuring quality teaching is highlighted by Honculada (2022), who emphasizes that instructional supervision should not be seen as fault-finding but rather as an opportunity for improvement.

However, challenges related to the limited number of supervisors, as noted by Mamo & Nigussa (2019), could potentially hinder the effectiveness of instructional supervision. This is especially relevant when there are few supervisors to manage the workload, which could affect the regularity and quality of observations. In this context, Weerakoon (2017) and Ebele & Olofu (2017) both pointed out the administrative load that supervisors face, which may contribute to inconsistency in supervision practices.

Moreover, the data also suggests that instructional supervision aligns with modern needs for 21st-century education, as emphasized by Nababan, Ardani, and Purba (2020). Supervisors are placing a strong emphasis on higher-order thinking skills, innovative teaching strategies, and the use of technology, reflecting a shift towards creating a learning environment that caters to the needs of today’s digital age.

The importance of collaboration in instructional supervision is also supported by the Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) Theory, which underscores the value of mutual trust, respect, and the quality of interactions between supervisors and teachers. This is evident in the teachers' perceptions of the effectiveness of lesson planning reviews and classroom observations, which foster a collaborative approach to professional development.

Overall, the mean of 4.22, categorized as Very High Extent (VHE), reflects a positive perception of the instructional supervision process. Supervisors are effectively contributing to the improvement of lesson planning and classroom management. To further enhance instructional supervision, it is important to address challenges related to the supervisor workload and continue fostering collaborative relationships between supervisors and teachers, as suggested by Arockiaraj et al. (2020). In doing so, the process of instructional supervision can better support teachers in adapting to the demands of 21st-century education, improving both teaching and learning outcomes.

The data in Table 9 shows the Immediacy of Feedback on Classroom Observation and the Adequacy of Feedback on Instructional Supervision. Both categories received high ratings, reflecting a "Very High Extent (VHE)" of implementation in the areas assessed.

Table 9. *Instructional Supervision in Terms of Dialogue and Discussion*

<i>Items</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
a. Immediacy of Feedback on Classroom Observation			
Instructional supervisor ...			
1. conducts supervisory conferences right after observing teachers	4.48	.73	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. provides immediate feedback after the teaching-learning process	4.47	.66	Very High Extent (VHE)
3. spends enough time to discuss teacher’s strengths and capabilities	4.38	.65	Very High Extent (VHE)
4. gives sufficient time to discuss teacher’s weaknesses and difficulties	4.35	.74	Very High Extent (VHE)
5. allots time to share supervisory experiences through constructive dialogue, mutual trust and shared expertise	4.35	.69	Very High Extent (VHE)
Composite	4.40	.62	Very High Extent (VHE)
b. Adequacy of Feedback on Instructional Supervision			
Instructional supervisor ...			
1. provides data-based feedback and responses	4.27	.84	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. gives appreciation and positive comments	4.47	.73	Very High Extent (VHE)
3. discusses teacher’s weaknesses and difficulties	4.38	.76	Very High Extent (VHE)
4. promotes two-way communication process	4.46	.74	Very High Extent (VHE)
5. supports curriculum and staff development	4.49	.71	Very High Extent (VHE)
Composite	4.41	.68	Very High Extent (VHE)
Overall	4.41	.63	Very High Extent (VHE)

Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Strongly Agree (Very High Extent - VHE); 3.41–4.20 – Agree (High Extent - HE); 2.61–3.40 – Moderately Agree (Moderate Extent - ME); 1.81–2.60 – Disagree (Low Extent - LE); 1.00–1.80 – Strongly Disagree (Very Low Extent - VLE)

The composite means for both categories are 4.40 (Immediacy of Feedback) and 4.41 (Adequacy of Feedback), indicating that instructional supervisors engage effectively in providing feedback to teachers.

The immediacy of feedback focuses on the promptness and effectiveness of feedback provided after classroom observations. The items in this category all received very high ratings, with the highest mean score of 4.48 for “Instructional supervisor conducts supervisory conferences right after observing teachers,” indicating that supervisors prioritize timely feedback. Other notable items in this category include providing immediate feedback after the teaching-learning process (4.47) and spending enough time to discuss teachers' strengths and capabilities (4.38). These findings align with the work of Tschannen-Moran & Hoy (2016), who emphasize that the timeliness and quality of feedback from instructional leaders significantly enhance teacher efficacy and learning outcomes.

On the other hand, the adequacy of feedback evaluates how well the feedback provided is adequate, constructive, and supportive. The highest mean score in this category is 4.49 for “Supports curriculum and staff development,” suggesting that supervisors excel in offering feedback that contributes to broader professional growth. Other high ratings include providing appreciation and positive comments (4.47) and promoting two-way communication (4.46). These aspects are critical for fostering a collaborative environment, as highlighted by Pomentel (2024), who notes that a two-way communication process creates a culture of trust and openness in schools. Amina (2015) mentioned that feedback was given through reports, queries about teachers' performance, and personal meetings to discuss issues like lesson preparation, class attendance, and reporting to the school. Supervisors, therefore, provide not only a diagnosis of teaching but also feedback that supports teachers' professional growth and development.

These results resonate with the views of scholars like Agus & Samuri (2018) and Gordon (2019), who emphasize that instructional supervision is vital for improving teaching practices and student learning outcomes. The findings also echo the perspectives of Oriente and Alvarado (2020), who assert that instructional supervision helps teachers address challenges, and Marzano (2019) and Harris & Muijs (2016), who stress the importance of ongoing feedback and a growth-oriented culture. Moreover, the high ratings for items related to teacher strengths and curriculum development highlight the effectiveness of feedback in promoting professional development, a central tenet of instructional leadership as described by Zarco (2024).

Overall, the data suggests that instructional supervisors are fulfilling their roles effectively, providing the necessary support for teachers' growth and development. The study confirms that when feedback is timely, transparent, and collaborative, it positively impacts teachers' professional performance, aligning with the broader goal of improving the quality of education. This reinforces the importance of instructional supervision in fostering a positive teaching environment, which ultimately enhances student learning outcomes.

Table 10. presents the results of the satisfaction and evaluation of instructional supervision, with a focus on both supervisory practices and the skills of instructional supervisors. The data indicate that teachers perceive instructional supervision as highly effective across various dimensions, as reflected by the overall composite means for both aspects.

Table 10. *Instructional Supervision in Terms of Satisfaction and Evaluation (Part A)*

Items	WM	SD	Interpretation
Satisfaction with Instructional Supervision			
As a Supervisee, I am satisfied with the following:			
Instructional Supervisory Practices based on the...			
1. overall quality of instructional supervision	4.26	.75	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. general organization of instructional supervision	4.28	.80	Very High Extent (VHE)
3. administrative support to instructional supervision	4.31	.76	Very High Extent (VHE)
4. objective evaluation of instructional supervision	4.20	.85	High Extent (HE)
5. cooperative action in instructional supervision	4.34	.77	Very High Extent (VHE)
Composite	4.28	.77	Very High Extent (VHE)
As a Supervisee, I am satisfied with the following:			
Instructional supervisor's ...			
1. planning skills on observing, monitoring and evaluating the instructional process	4.26	.74	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. analytical skills to explain the relationship that exist between teaching and learning	4.30	.76	Very High Extent (VHE)
3. social competence in building collaborative and empowering relationships	4.21	.81	Very High Extent (VHE)
4. communicative competence on holding one-on-one conferences with teachers	4.30	.71	Very High Extent (VHE)
5. creative and innovative skills in dealing with complex classroom practices	4.18	.80	High Extent (HE)
Composite	4.25	.73	Very High Extent (VHE)

Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Strongly Agree (Very High Extent - VHE); 3.41–4.20 – Agree (High Extent - HE); 2.61–3.40 – Moderately Agree (Moderate Extent - ME); 1.81–2.60 – Disagree (Low Extent - LE); 1.00–1.80 – Strongly Disagree (Very Low Extent - VLE)

In terms of Satisfaction with Instructional Supervisory Practices, the item with the highest mean was “Cooperative action in instructional supervision” (mean = 4.34) with a very high extent (VHE) of implementation, indicating that teachers perceive a very high level of satisfaction with the collaborative efforts involved in the supervisory process. This highlights the importance of teamwork and mutual support between supervisors and teachers, aligning with the findings of Pomentel (2024), who emphasized the need for collaborative supervision to build trust and foster a supportive environment for teachers. These results also resonate with the views of Agus & Samuri (2018), who argue that a strong, supportive supervisory framework contributes to the improvement of teaching practices and student learning.

The item “administrative support to instructional supervision” also received a high mean rating of 4.31, with a very high extent (VHE)

of implementation. This suggests that teachers value the organizational backing and resources provided for supervision, which align with the findings of Benigno (2016), who emphasized that effective administrative support is crucial for enhancing teaching and learning processes.

On the other hand, Satisfaction with Instructional Supervisor’s Skills shows similarly high satisfaction, with the highest mean for the item “Analytical skills to explain the relationship that exists between teaching and learning” (mean = 4.30) with a very high extent (VHE) of implementation. This indicates that teachers highly value their supervisor’s ability to connect instructional practices to student outcomes, supporting the work of Gordon (2019), who highlighted the role of instructional supervision in improving teachers’ decision-making and problem-solving abilities. Additionally, the item “communicative competence on holding one-on-one conferences with teachers” received a high mean rating of 4.30, aligning with the views of Pomentel (2024) and Marzano (2019), who emphasize that effective instructional leaders must cultivate strong, collaborative relationships with teachers to foster professional growth. This finding also resonates with Blumer’s Symbolic Interactionism Theory (1997), which provides a framework for understanding how instructional leaders’ supervisory practices can impact teachers’ work performance. According to Blumer, this theory explains how meaning is derived from social interactions. Symbolic interactionism highlights the importance of interpersonal interactions and the use of symbols in communication, suggesting that the self is constructed through these interactions. Blumer argued that people form human groups and that their interactions, through the approval, arrangement, and redefinition of common symbols, shape their shared reality. In the context of instructional supervision, these interactions, particularly those involving meaningful one-on-one conversations, help to shape teachers’ perceptions of their roles and influence their professional development.

Overall, the composite means for both sections—Satisfaction with Instructional Supervisory Practices (4.28) and Satisfaction with Instructional Supervisor’s Skills (4.25)—further confirm that teachers are highly satisfied with the current supervisory practices and the skills of their supervisors. These findings reflect the effectiveness of the supervisory process in promoting teacher development and reinforcing a culture of continuous improvement, in line with the research of Zarco (2024), who underscores the importance of transparency, feedback, and ongoing professional support in instructional supervision.

In conclusion, the data from Table 8 highlights the strong positive perceptions of teachers regarding both the supervisory practices and the skills of their instructional supervisors. This supports the idea that effective instructional supervision, characterized by clear communication, collaborative action, and targeted professional development, plays a pivotal role in enhancing teacher performance and ultimately improving student learning outcomes. As supported by the literature, continuing to refine and enhance these practices will lead to sustained improvements in both teacher and student success.

The data from Table 11 shows that instructional supervision is evaluated positively across all items, with high mean ratings for various aspects.

Table 11. *Instructional Supervision in Terms of Satisfaction and Evaluation (Part B)*

Items	WM	SD	Interpretation
Evaluation of Instructional Supervision			
a. Based on my observation, the instructional supervisor accomplishes the appraisal forms through:			
1. conducting lesson plan reviews	4.43	.82	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. performing classroom observations	4.45	.76	Very High Extent (VHE)
3. examining classroom discipline or management	4.37	.84	Very High Extent (VHE)
4. checking the routine management	4.26	.83	Very High Extent (VHE)
5. monitoring the record management	4.26	.87	Very High Extent (VHE)
Composite	4.36	.79	Very High Extent (VHE)
As a Supervisee, I am satisfied with the following:			
b. Based on my observation, the instructional supervisor prepares the supervisory reports through:			
1. accomplishing the observation form upon the observation of the teaching-learning process	4.21	.86	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. monitoring the class targets or accomplishments	4.29	.80	Very High Extent (VHE)
3. reviewing IPCRF as part of performance monitoring and tracking	4.15	.84	High Extent (HE)
4. keeping the appraisal forms for record management and future reference	4.21	.79	Very High Extent (VHE)
5. assessing the realization of government’s instructional policies and practices	4.23	.77	Very High Extent (VHE)
Composite	4.22	.76	Very High Extent (VHE)
Overall	4.28	.71	Very High Extent (VHE)

Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Strongly Agree (Very High Extent - VHE); 3.41–4.20 – Agree (High Extent - HE); 2.61–3.40 – Moderately Agree (Moderate Extent - ME); 1.81–2.60 – Disagree (Low Extent - LE); 1.00–1.80 – Strongly Disagree (Very Low Extent - VLE)

The composite means for evaluating instructional supervision is 4.36, indicating a very high extent of accomplishment. Specifically, “performing classroom observations” received the highest mean score of 4.45, reflecting its importance in the supervisory process. This aligns with This aligns with Allida et al. (2018), who emphasized the necessity of regular, periodic classroom observations for effective instructional supervision. Similarly, “conducting lesson plan reviews” received a mean of 4.43, underscoring the value of planning and preparation in enhancing teaching effectiveness, in line with Abdeta (2018), who argued that regular follow-up activities,

including lesson plan reviews, are crucial for teacher development.

In addition, “examining classroom discipline or management” received 4.37, showing that effective supervision also includes ensuring a conducive learning environment, consistent with the findings of Maisyaroh et al. (2018), who noted that supervisors should not only strive to look for errors but also provide enough support to improve or increase teacher competence. Furthermore, “monitoring record management” and “checking routine management”, both with a mean of 4.26, reflecting the importance of organizational aspects in the supervisory process, although slightly less emphasized than direct instructional practices. This supports the argument by Weerakoon (2017), who pointed out that one of the major problems faced by school supervisors is the administrative load delineated to them.

In terms of satisfaction with the preparation of supervisory reports, the composite mean is 4.22, indicating that supervisees are very satisfied with the supervisor's practices. The highest-rated item was “monitoring class targets/accomplishments” with a mean of 4.29, which reflects the importance of tracking progress and outcomes, as emphasized by Abdeta (2018) mentioned that the absence of follow-up activities of teachers and the giving of timely feedback are the challenges that occur in the practice of school-based supervision. Other items, such as “accomplishing observation form” (mean = 4.21) and “assessing the realization of government’s instructional policies” (mean = 4.23), were also highly rated, indicating satisfaction with structured and formal processes in instructional supervision. This finding is consistent with Sulisworo (2016), who highlighted that principals must have the capacity to lead teachers and institute school programs that would enhance creativity and innovation so that teachers can adapt to the digital age. These high ratings suggest that the instructional supervisor is viewed as highly effective in both evaluation and reporting, fostering a positive and collaborative environment for teacher development. Overall, the data suggests that the instructional supervisor is highly regarded for both the thoroughness of evaluation and the detailed reporting practices, which foster a collaborative and supportive environment for teachers’ professional growth.

The data presented in Table 12 reveals the extent of implementation of various aspects of instructional supervision in the study. The overall mean of 4.30 with a standard deviation of 0.14 indicates a very high level of implementation, suggesting that instructional supervision is carried out effectively with minimal variation across responses.

Table 12. Summary of the Extent of Implementation of Instructional Supervision

Variables	WM	SD	Interpretation
1. Concept and Purpose	4.48	.47	Very High Extent (VHE)
2. Planning and Preparations	4.12	.57	High Extent (HE)
3. Organization and Implementation	4.22	.73	Very High Extent (VHE)
4. Dialogue and Discussion	4.41	.63	Very High Extent (VHE)
5. Satisfaction and Evaluation	4.28	.71	Very High Extent (VHE)
Overall	4.30	.14	Very High Extent (VHE)

Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Strongly Agree (Very High Extent - VHE); 3.41–4.20 – Agree (High Extent - HE); 2.61–3.40 – Moderately Agree (Moderate Extent - ME); 1.81–2.60 – Disagree (Low Extent - LE); 1.00–1.80 – Strongly Disagree (Very Low Extent - VLE)

The highest mean was recorded in the Concept and Purpose category, with a score of 4.48 and a standard deviation of 0.47, reflecting that respondents have a strong understanding of the objectives and significance of instructional supervision. This aligns with the work of Honculada (2022), who noted that a clear understanding of the purpose is crucial for effective supervision. The Dialogue and Discussion component also scored highly, with a mean of 4.41 and a standard deviation of 0.63, suggesting that there is significant engagement between supervisors and teachers, fostering a positive environment for communication, as emphasized by Allida et al. (2018).

The Satisfaction and Evaluation aspect received a mean of 4.28, reflecting very high satisfaction with the evaluation process and feedback received from supervisors. The findings echo Maisyaroh et al. (2018), who emphasized that constructive feedback is vital for teacher development. Organization and Implementation received a score of 4.22, indicating a very high extent of implementation, though the slightly higher standard deviation of 0.73 suggests some variability in how these activities are carried out, which is consistent with the observations of Sulisworo (2016) regarding the importance of organized leadership in instructional supervision.

The Planning and Preparations category had the lowest score of 4.12, with a standard deviation of 0.57, still reflecting a high level of implementation but with potential areas for improvement in terms of planning and preparation. This is consistent with the work of Ebele and Olofu (2017), who highlighted that quality and continuity in planning are crucial but often challenged by limited resources and time. Overall, the results indicate that instructional supervision is implemented to a very high extent across the various components, with the highest scores in areas related to clarity of purpose, dialogue, and evaluation. These findings support the conclusion of Allida et al. (2018), who emphasized that comprehensive, effective, and regular instructional supervision is essential for achieving school goals and enhancing teacher performance.

Problem 3. Are there significant differences in the perceived extent of Implementation of their School Heads’ Instructional Supervision among the respondents in terms of their: Length of Teaching Experience, Educational Attainment, and Teaching Position?

In Table 13, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine if there were significant differences in the respondents’ perceived extent of instructional supervision based on their length of teaching experience.

Table 13. *Analysis of Variance in the Respondents' Perceived Extent of Implementation of Their School Heads' Instructional Supervision Based on Their Length of Teaching Experiences*

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision	Remarks
Concept and Purpose	Between Groups	3.92	4	.98	4.96	.001	Reject H_{01}	S
	Within Groups	22.93	116	.20				
	Total	26.85	120					
Planning and Preparations	Between Groups	4.28	4	1.07	3.64	.008	Reject H_{01}	S
	Within Groups	34.15	116	.29				
	Total	38.43	120					
Organization and Implementation	Between Groups	3.58	4	.89	1.71	.152	Fail to Reject H_{01}	NS
	Within Groups	60.63	116	.52				
	Total	64.21	120					
Dialogue and Discussion	Between Groups	4.40	4	1.10	3.00	.021	Reject H_{01}	S
	Within Groups	42.63	116	.37				
	Total	47.03	120					
Satisfaction and Evaluation	Between Groups	5.49	4	1.37	2.82	.028	Reject H_{01}	S
	Within Groups	56.37	116	.49				
	Total	61.86	120					

differences between groups are statistically significant at p-value < 0.05; S- Significant, NS – Not Significant

For Concept and Purpose, the F-value of 4.96 with a p-value of 0.001 is significant, suggesting that there is a statistically significant difference between groups with varying lengths of teaching experience. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected. This means the length of teaching experience influences how teachers perceive the clarity and purpose of instructional supervision, which aligns with the findings of Sulisworo (2016), who highlighted that experienced educators tend to have a deeper understanding of the goals and benefits of instructional supervision. Also, this aligns with the findings of Abdeta (2018), who emphasized the importance of follow-up activities and timely feedback in the practice of school-based supervision, suggesting that experienced teachers are likely to better understand the broader goals of instructional supervision and its importance. Furthermore, Weerakoon (2017) highlights how administrative burdens can impact the clarity of these concepts, yet experienced teachers may have developed coping mechanisms that allow them to perceive these concepts more clearly.

Similarly, Planning and Preparations showed a significant difference, with an F-value of 3.64 and a p-value of 0.008. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected. There is a significant difference in the perceived extent of implementation based on the length of teaching experience. This suggests that respondents' length of teaching experience also impacts how they perceive the planning and preparation involved in instructional supervision. Ebele and Olofu (2017) emphasized that more experienced teachers tend to be more involved in planning and have higher expectations for supervisory support. Nababan et al. (2020) underscore the need for teachers to transform themselves to adapt to technological advancements, which often require careful planning. This transformation may be more evident in experienced teachers, who are likely to feel more comfortable integrating new tools and methods into their teaching and supervision practices.

The Organization and Implementation component, however, yielded an F-value of 1.71 with a p-value of 0.152. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the researcher fail to reject the null hypothesis. There is no significant difference in the perceived extent of implementation based on the length of teaching experience. This indicates that the length of teaching experience does not significantly influence how respondents perceive the organization and implementation of instructional supervision. This result may be consistent with the findings of Maisyaroh et al. (2018), who found that the organizational aspects of supervision were often perceived similarly across different experience levels, suggesting a standardized approach in many school systems. This finding also resonates with Maisyaroh et al. (2020), who noted that despite different supervision techniques, organizational practices tend to be standardized across teaching levels, with less variance based on experience. Teachers, regardless of their experience, may perceive these stages of supervision as largely administrative and less subject to individual perception.

For Dialogue and Discussion, the F-value of 3.00 and p-value of 0.021. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference in the perceived extent of implementation based on the length of teaching experience, meaning that teachers with different lengths of experience perceive the level and quality of dialogue and discussion with their school heads differently. This is consistent with Ghamrawi et al. (2019), who observed that experienced teachers are more likely to value the feedback and collaboration that occurs through dialogue in supervision. Additionally, Allida et al. (2018) emphasized the importance of trust and mutual respect in supervision, suggesting that experienced teachers, who have had more opportunities to develop such relationships, might view dialogue as a more essential component of the process.

Finally, Satisfaction and Evaluation also showed a statistically significant result, with an F-value of 2.82 and a p-value of 0.028. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference in the perceived extent of implementation based on the length of teaching experience. This suggests that the length of teaching experience impacts how satisfied teachers are with the evaluation process and the feedback they receive. Experienced teachers are likely to have more specific expectations for feedback,

as noted by Honculada (2022), who pointed out that satisfaction with supervision tends to increase with experience, as teachers become more attuned to the nuances of effective evaluations. Ebele and Olofu (2017) noted the challenges that arise from the limited number of supervisors and the administrative tasks they are burdened with, which can affect how teachers perceive the evaluation process. More experienced teachers may have a clearer understanding of the evaluation criteria and how they are applied, which may lead to higher satisfaction levels, especially if they have seen improvements in their teaching over time through the process.

These findings underscore that the length of teaching experience plays a role in how teachers perceive various aspects of instructional supervision. Experienced teachers are likely to have different expectations and perceptions regarding the purpose, planning, dialogue, and evaluation of supervision, which may reflect their deeper understanding of the processes involved. The lack of significant difference in the perception of organization and implementation could suggest that these aspects of instructional supervision are perceived as more standardized, regardless of experience level.

In conclusion, the study supports the idea that instructional supervision practices should be adaptable to teachers' experience levels, particularly in areas like purpose, planning, and evaluation. By aligning supervisory practices with the evolving needs of teachers at different career stages, school heads can ensure more effective and meaningful supervision.

In Table 14, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine if there were significant differences in the respondents' perceived extent of instructional supervision based on their educational attainment.

Table 14. *Analysis of Variance in the Respondents' Perceived Extent of Implementation of Their School Heads' Instructional Supervision Based on Their Educational Attainment*

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision	Remarks
Concept and Purpose	Between Groups	4.35	5	.87	4.44	.001	Reject H ₀₂	S
	Within Groups	22.50	115	.20				
	Total	26.85	120					
Planning and Preparations	Between Groups	1.66	5	.33	1.04	.400	Fail to Reject H ₀₂	NS
	Within Groups	36.78	115	.32				
	Total	38.43	120					
Organization and Implementation	Between Groups	2.95	5	.59	1.11	.359	Fail to Reject H ₀₂	NS
	Within Groups	61.25	115	.53				
	Total	64.21	120					
Dialogue and Discussion	Between Groups	4.25	5	.85	2.28	.051	Fail to Reject H ₀₂	NS
	Within Groups	42.78	115	.37				
	Total	47.03	120					
Satisfaction and Evaluation	Between Groups	4.69	5	.94	1.89	.102	Fail to Reject H ₀₂	NS
	Within Groups	57.17	115	.50				
	Total	61.86	120					

differences between groups are statistically significant at p-value < 0.05; S- Significant, NS – Not Significant

The analysis reveals a significant difference in the perceived extent of implementation in the area of "Concept and Purpose" of instructional supervision, as evidenced by a p-value of .001, which is less than the threshold of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H₀₂) is rejected. Teachers with varying educational backgrounds perceive the concept and purpose of instructional supervision differently. This suggests that respondents with different educational attainments perceive the clarity and relevance of the concept and purpose of instructional supervision differently. This finding is consistent with the study by Comighud et al. (2020), which highlighted that the perceived effectiveness of instructional supervision can vary based on teachers' educational backgrounds, with those holding advanced degrees having more favorable views on the purpose and execution of supervision. This reflects the broader trend, as noted by Zarco (2024), that more highly educated teachers may have a more refined understanding of the strategic and conceptual aspects of supervision. This also ties in with the idea that instructional leaders, as identified by Osman and Kamis (2019), need to adapt their approaches to meet the evolving educational needs of teachers, especially in a context where educational reforms are ongoing.

However, the results show no significant differences in the areas of "Planning and Preparations" (p-value = 0.400), "Organization and Implementation" (p-value = 0.359), and "Satisfaction and Evaluation" (p-value = 0.102). Hence, the researcher fail to reject the null hypothesis (H₀₂) in these variables. These areas, although critical to instructional supervision, do not appear to vary significantly across educational attainment levels. This suggests that regardless of the educational background, teachers may perceive the planning, organizational, and evaluation processes of instructional supervision similarly. This finding aligns with the work of Mamo & Nigussa (2019), who observed that the number of supervisors and available resources can influence the quality of instructional supervision, rather than educational attainment alone.

The area of "Dialogue and Discussion" shows a p-value of 0.051, which is marginally above the 0.05 significance level. While this result is not statistically significant, it does suggest a trend that may warrant further investigation. The perception of communication and dialogue between supervisors and teachers is essential in fostering a collaborative and growth-oriented environment, as discussed

by Pomentel (2024) and Tschannen-Moran & Hoy (2016). The slight difference observed may reflect a growing recognition of the importance of ongoing dialogue in instructional supervision, as highlighted by these authors. Nevertheless, the null hypothesis (H_0) in this variable is still accepted.

Overall, the analysis suggests that while the educational attainment of teachers may influence their perception of certain aspects of instructional supervision, other factors, such as experience, resources, and the supervisor's approach, also play significant roles in shaping these perceptions. The findings highlight the importance of ongoing professional development and personalized supervision strategies to meet the needs of teachers at different stages of their careers.

The results from Table 15, which presents the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) based on respondents' teaching positions, reveal significant differences in the perceived extent of the implementation of their school heads' instructional supervision in certain areas, while others show no statistically significant differences. Educational reforms over the past years have emphasized the need to revisit and enhance instructional leaders' current supervision schemes to keep pace with innovations in education (Osman & Kamis, 2019). This underscores the importance of refining instructional supervision practices to reflect these changes.

Table 15. *Analysis of Variance in the Respondents' Perceived Extent of Implementation of Their School Heads' Instructional Supervision Based on Their Teaching Positions*

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision	Remarks
Concept and Purpose	Between Groups	4.36	3	1.45	7.57	.000	Reject H_0	S
	Within Groups	22.49	117	.19				
	Total	26.85	120					
Planning and Preparations	Between Groups	5.02	3	1.67	5.86	.001	Reject H_0	S
	Within Groups	33.41	117	.29				
	Total	38.43	120					
Organization and Implementation	Between Groups	3.90	3	1.30	2.52	.061	Fail to Reject H_0	NS
	Within Groups	60.30	117	.52				
	Total	64.21	120					
Dialogue and Discussion	Between Groups	2.90	3	.97	2.56	.058	Fail to Reject H_0	NS
	Within Groups	44.13	117	.38				
	Total	47.03	120					
Satisfaction and Evaluation	Between Groups	1.88	3	.63	1.22	.305	Fail to Reject H_0	NS
	Within Groups	59.98	117	.51				
	Total	61.86	120					

differences between groups are statistically significant at p-value < 0.05; S- Significant, NS – Not Significant

In the area of Concept and Purpose, the p-value of 0.000 indicates a statistically significant difference between groups, suggesting that teachers in different positions perceive the concept and purpose of instructional supervision differently. This finding aligns with the literature, which highlights that a clear understanding of the goals behind instructional supervision is crucial for its success (Glickman, Gordon, & Ross-Gordon, 2018). More experienced teachers, such as lead teachers or department heads, may have a clearer understanding of the goals due to their more substantial experience and involvement in the process. As Tulowitzki (2019) points out, supervision has evolved from bureaucratic practices to more participatory approaches, and this evolution could explain the differing perceptions based on teaching positions.

For Planning and Preparations, the p-value of 0.001 also indicates a significant difference, with teachers in various positions perceiving the planning and preparation of instructional supervision differently. Senior teachers or those involved in planning may have a more favorable view of these preparations, as their involvement grants them greater insight. This is consistent with previous research, including that of Comighud et al. (2020), which emphasizes that teacher involvement in the planning phase can positively influence their perceptions of the supervisory process. Moreover, the importance of instructional supervision in enhancing teaching practices is highlighted by Agus & Samuri (2018), who argue that supervisors play a key role in reinforcing effective teaching to improve student learning outcomes.

In contrast, Organization and Implementation shows a p-value of 0.061, which is slightly above the commonly accepted significance level of 0.05. This result suggests a trend, but not a statistically significant difference, in how teachers from different positions perceive the organization and execution of instructional supervision. However, the absence of a significant difference may imply that these elements of supervision are generally perceived similarly across teaching positions. According to Zarco (2024), effective instructional supervision is a constant process aimed at improving teaching and learning, and consistency in its organization might reflect this ongoing process.

Dialogue and Discussion approaches significance, with a p-value of 0.058. This suggests that there may be differences in the extent of dialogue and discussion between teachers and school heads based on teaching positions. Teachers in leadership roles might experience more frequent and meaningful interactions with school heads. Pomentel (2024) emphasizes the importance of collaborative supervision,

with ongoing dialogue and problem-solving to foster a supportive environment. This finding aligns with existing research that shows how open communication contributes to a collaborative and growth-oriented environment (Hoy & Davis, 2019).

Finally, in the area of Satisfaction and Evaluation, the p-value of 0.305 reveals no statistically significant difference among teaching positions, indicating that teachers, regardless of their role, tend to perceive the satisfaction and evaluation process similarly. This suggests that other factors, such as personal experiences or the overall school culture, may have a greater influence on how teachers perceive the effectiveness of supervision. As noted by Zarco (2024), teachers' acceptance and interaction with supervisors are crucial for the success of supervision. The overall lack of significant differences in satisfaction may point to the universal importance of transparent feedback and continuous support.

In summary, the ANOVA results show that teaching positions influence teachers' perceptions of certain aspects of instructional supervision, particularly the concept and purpose, and planning and preparation. However, in areas like organization and implementation, dialogue and discussion, and satisfaction and evaluation, there are no significant differences across teaching positions. This suggests that while teachers' roles may impact how certain elements of supervision are perceived, many aspects of instructional supervision are viewed similarly by teachers regardless of their position. As Benigno (2016) asserts, instructional supervision is essential for the professional development of teachers, and school leaders should consider both teachers' specific roles and the broader supervisory context when implementing these practices. This aligns with the findings of Comighud et al. (2020), who stress the importance of supporting novice teachers with resources and guidance to enhance their supervision experience.

Conclusions

Public school teachers exhibit diverse teaching experiences, educational attainments, and career stages, with most in mid-career and holding entry-level positions, while a smaller group has pursued advanced studies or leadership roles. Instructional supervision by school heads is perceived as "Very High," especially in "Concept and Purpose" and "Dialogue and Discussion," though "Planning and Preparation" shows room for improvement. Teachers' perceptions vary with teaching experience, particularly in areas like "Concept and Purpose" and "Dialogue and Discussion," reflecting differences in expectations and understanding. Educational attainment influences views on "Concept and Purpose," while perceptions of other areas remain consistent. Similarly, teaching positions affect views on "Concept and Purpose" and "Planning and Preparation," emphasizing the need for tailored yet transparent supervision practices across roles.

On the bases of the findings and conclusions drawn, the followings are recommended:

To support teachers at all career stages, professional development programs should be personalized to different experience levels. For early-career teachers, mentoring and support for progressing through Teacher I roles should be emphasized, while for mid-career teachers, opportunities for leadership training and further specialization should be prioritized. Additionally, schools should encourage further academic advancement by providing incentives or funding for teachers to complete their graduate studies and doctoral degrees.

While instructional supervision is largely effective, the area of "Planning and Preparations" shows room for improvement. School leaders should invest in strengthening planning processes by offering professional development on effective instructional planning, involving teachers more in the planning phases, and providing necessary resources to ensure comprehensive preparation. Maintaining focus on the strengths of "Concept and Purpose" and "Dialogue and Discussion" is crucial for further enhancing teacher engagement and performance.

Given that experienced teachers have different expectations and perceptions, it is important for school heads to consider these varying perspectives when implementing instructional supervision. Supervisory practices should be flexible, acknowledging the expertise of senior teachers while also offering guidance and support to those in the early stages of their careers. Differentiated supervision can help meet the diverse needs of teachers based on their experience.

Since teachers with higher educational attainment show more favorable views towards the "Concept and Purpose" of instructional supervision, it is recommended that schools emphasize ongoing professional development and educational advancement for teachers at all levels. This can help improve overall understanding and engagement with the goals of instructional supervision. Schools could also explore ways to bridge any gaps in perception by creating opportunities for cross-level discussions and learning.

Instructional supervision practices should be tailored to the specific needs of teachers at different levels of seniority. More senior teachers should be provided with opportunities for leadership roles in supervision, enabling them to mentor and guide their peers. At the same time, consistent and transparent approaches to supervision should be maintained across all roles to ensure equity and inclusiveness. Supervisors should also foster collaboration between teachers of different positions to share insights and promote a unified approach to instructional improvement.

References

Agus, R., & Samuri, S. M. (2018). Learning Analytics Contribution in Education and Child Development: A Review on Learning. *Asian Journal of Assessment in Teaching And Learning*, 8, 36-47. <https://doi.org/10.37134/Ajatel.Vol8.4.2018>

- Aldeeb, H.M. (2018). Impact of Accumulated Teaching Experience on Supporting Learners in Higher Education: A Case Study from Bahrain. *Social Science Learning Education Journal*.
- Allida, V., Olela, M., Ogwari, P., & Minia, O. (2018). Best Practices In Instructional Supervision: A Study Of Adventist Secondary Schools In Ranen Conference. *Baraton Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 8(Special Issue), 1-7. Retrieved from <https://www.ueab.ac.ke/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/Vencie-Michael-Peter-Onesmo.pdf>
- Amina, J. (2015). An Evaluation Of Head Teachers' Performance In Supervision Of Instruction And Involvement Of Staff In Decision-Making In The School. *International Journal Of Research In Humanities And Social Studies*, 2(7), July 2015.
- Balanquit, E.P., Ladia, M.A., & Nool, N.R. (2023). The Influence of Faculty Members' Educational Attainment on the Performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) among State Universities and Colleges in the Philippines. *Journal of Curriculum and Teaching*.
- Bauer, T. N., & Erdogan, B. (2015). Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) Theory: An Introduction And Overview. *Oxford Handbook Of Leader-Member Exchange*, 3-9.
- Benigno, S. (2016). A Viable Solution To Implementing Effective Instructional Supervision. *Journal Of Education And Learning*, 5(1), 128-132. Retrieved From <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1097793>
- Comighud, S. M. T., Fualan, M. C. Z., & Cordevilla, R. P. (2020). Instructional Supervision And Performance Evaluation: A Correlation Of Factors. *UBT International Conference*, 193. Retrieved From https://knowledgecenter.ubt-uni.net/conference/2020/all_events/193
- Department Of Education. (2015). Deped Order No. 2. Guidelines On The Establishment And Implementation Of The Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) In The Department Of Education. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/>
- Department Of Education. (2017). Deped Order No. 42 National Adoption And Implementation Of The Philippine Professional Standards For Teachers. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/>
- Ebele, U., & Olufu, P. (2017). Enhancing The Standard Of Teaching And Learning In The 21st Century Via Qualitative School-Based Supervision In Secondary Schools In Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). *International Journal Of Educational Administration And Policy Studies*, 9(6), 79-83.
- Ghamrawi, N., Ghamrawi, N., & Shal, T. (2019). Differentiated Education Supervision Approaches In Schools Through The Lens Of Teachers. *International Journal For Innovation Education And Research*. Retrieved From <https://ijer.net/ijer/article/view/2011>
- Gordon, S. P. (2019). Educational Supervision: Reflections On Its Past, Present, And Future. *Journal Of Educational Supervision*, 2(2), 27-52. Retrieved From <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1250310>
- Hasim, A. T., Guiamalon, T. S., & Boquia, A. H. (2020). Administrative Competence Of School Heads Of The Ministry Of Basic, Higher And Technical Education (MBHTE) In Bangsamoro Autonomous Region In Muslim Mindanao (BARMM).
- Honculada, S. (2022). Teachers' Perceptions On The Instructional Supervisory Practices Of Instructional Leaders: Basis For Capacity Building And Retooling On Supervisory Principles And Roles.
- Hoque, K. E., Kenavathulla, H. B., Subramaniam, M. V., & Islam, R. (2020). Relationships Between Supervision And Teachers' Performance And Attitude In Secondary Schools In Malaysia. *Sage Open*, 10(2), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020925501>
- Hussein, A.M. (2021). The Impact of Educational Attainment on Individual Earning and Social Class Mobility. *GeographyRN: Social Organization (Sub-Topic)*.
- Irawan, D., Wahyudin, A., & Yanto, H. (2018). The Moderating Influence Of Academic Supervision Of Teacher Competencies And Commitment Towards Organizational Teacher Performance. *Educational Management*, 7(1), 64-70. Retrieved From <https://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/eduman/article/view/27749>
- Kini, T., & Podolsky, A. (2016). Does Teaching Experience Increase Teacher Effectiveness? A Review Of The Research. *Learning Policy Institute*. Retrieved From <https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/our-work/publications-resources/teaching-experience-increase-teacher-effectiveness-review-research>
- Laabidi, Y. (2021). Influence Of Teaching Experience On Teachers' Level Of Use Of Critical Thinking. *Lit Journal: A Journal on Language and Language Teaching*.
- Lasig, W. (2023). Instructional Supervisory Practices And Behavior Of School Heads: Its Relation To The Work Performance Of Elementary School Teachers. *International Journal Of Research Publications*, 129(1), 55-73. <https://doi.org/10.47119/IJRP1001291720235248>
- Lee, S.W., & Lee, E. (2020). Teacher qualification matters: The association between cumulative teacher qualification and students'

educational attainment. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 77, 102218.

Limon, M. (2015). Role Performance Of TLE Supervisors: Its Implications To Supervisory Practices In University Settings. *International Journal Of Vocational And Technical Education Research*, 1(3), 35-44.

Maisyaroh, B., Wiyono, B. B., Hardika, A., Mangorsi, S., & Canapi, S. (2021). The Implementation Of Instructional Supervision In Indonesia And The Philippines, And Its Effect On The Variation Of Teacher Learning Models And Materials. *Cogent Education*, 8(1), 1962232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2021.1962232>

Mamo, T. R., & Nigusso, G. (2019). The Practices And Challenges Of Internal School Supervision: The Case In East Wollega Secondary Schools. *International Journal Of Multidisciplinary Research And Development*.

Marzano, R. J. (2019). *The New Art And Science Of Teaching*. Solution Tree Press.

Mendoza, J., & Hife, L. (2020). Educational Leaders Practices And School Culture In CALABARZON State Universities And Colleges. *International Journal Of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 11(12), 603–617. <https://www.ijser.org/researchpaper/>

Mufidah, N., Arafat, Y., & Puspita, Y. (2021). The Effect of Training and Teaching Experience on Teacher's Performance. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Education Universitas PGRI Palembang (INCoEPP 2021)*.

Nyatsikor, M.K., Sosu, E.M., Mtika, P., & Robson, D. (2020). Teacher Characteristics and Children's Educational Attainment in Ghana: Do Some Teacher Characteristics Matter More for Children Attending Disadvantaged Schools? *Frontiers in Education*.

Ogbo, R. N. (2015). Effects Of Modified Clinical Supervision Approach On Teacher Instructional Performance In Ebonyi State. *Journal Of Educational Leadership*, 4(4), 54-59.

Oriente, V. S., & Alvarado, A. (2020). Supervisory Assistance In Organization: Basis For Enhanced Instructional Supervision For Teachers. *Journal Of Technology And Humanities*, 1(1), 11-17. <https://doi.org/10.53797/jthkks.v1i1.2.2020>

Pescuela, C. (2015). Extent Of School Administrators' Implementation Of Instructional Leadership And Its Relationship To Their Teachers' Performance. Thesis, Foundation University, Dumaguete City.

Pomentel, L. D. (2024). Exploring The Influence Of School Heads' Instructional Supervision On Teachers' Efficacy And Performance. *International Journal Of Research Publications*, 148(1), 256-275. <https://doi.org/10.47119/IJRP1001481520246420>

Rees, R. (2015). Beginning Teachers' Perceptions Of Their Novice Year Of Teaching. *All Graduate Theses And Dissertations*, Paper 4229.

Republic Act No. 9155. An Act Instituting A Framework Of Governance For Basic Education, Establishing Authority And Accountability, Renaming The Department Of Education, Culture And Sports As The Department Of Education, And For Other Purposes. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2001/08/11/Republic-Act-No-9155/>

Sergiovanni, T. J., & Starratt, R. J. (2007). *Supervision: A redefinition* (8th Ed.). New York: McGraw Hill.

Sulisworo, D. (2016). The Contribution Of The Education System Quality To Improve The Nation's Competitiveness Of Indonesia. *Journal Of Education And Learning (Edulearn)*, 10(2), 127-138.

Torres, R. (2016). Administration and Leadership Behavior of Elementary School Principals in Relation to Teachers' and Pupils' Performance. Thesis. Foundation University

Tschannen-Moran, M., & Hoy, A. W. (2016). *Teacher Efficacy: Capturing An Elusive Construct* (2nd Ed.). Routledge.

Tulowitzki, P. (2019). Supporting Instructional Leadership And School Improvement? Reflections On School Supervision From A German Perspective. *Journal Of Educational Administration*, 57(5), 571-581. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-03-2019-0040>

Zarco, K. (2024). Conduct Of Regular Instructional Supervision In Improving The Performance Of Teachers In Classroom Instructions And Management. *International Journal Of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies*, 4(7).

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Vincent R. Cailing

Division of Misamis Oriental
Department of Education – Philippines

Diana A. Amper

Division of Bukidnon
Department of Education – Philippines

Hairah O. Ali

Division of Iligan City
Department of Education – Philippines

Marie Gold C. Alonsabe

Division of Cagayan De Oro City
Department of Education – Philippines

Carlos T. Basadre

Capitol University – Philippines

Olga C. Alonsabe, PhD

Capitol University – Philippines